

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: YAKUBU MOHAMMED****FIRST NAME: ABDULRAHMAN****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied XUS UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author Xdid did *not* use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author Xdid did *not* use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. What is the primary method recommended for avoiding plagiarism?

- Properly cite the author or source of any information, whether a quote, paraphrase, statistic, or visual.¹**
- Always paraphrase information instead of quoting it directly, regardless of the source.
- Avoid using any sources of information entirely to prevent the risk of plagiarism.
- Only credit the author if the information is directly quoted from the source.

2. What is the critical difference between making an argument face-to-face and writing?

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 5th ed (Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024), 34.

- In writing, you must anticipate and respond to your readers' questions on their behalf.²**
- In face-to-face conversations, you must rely solely on rhetorical strategies to persuade your audience.
- Face-to-face discussions do not require the use of evidence to support claims.
- Writing allows for more flexibility in offering claims without the need for support.
3. What is the primary strategy for overcoming procrastination when writing a research paper?
- Drafting the entire paper in one marathon session.
- Substituting more reading for writing.
- Waiting until inspiration strikes to begin writing.
- Setting small, achievable goals and writing regularly.³**
4. In which of the following situations would you most likely use a "Selected Bibliography"?
- When you want to include every work you cite in your text.
- When you want to create a bibliography that lists works by only one person.
- When you want to save space or omit minor references that are unlikely to interest readers.⁴**

² Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 9th ed (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 56–57.

³ Turabian, 76.

⁴ Turabian, 155.

- When you want to annotate each bibliography entry with a brief description.
5. What is a potential risk even if you accurately cite a source in your bibliography or reference list?
- Failing to use a reliable source.
- Using the source's exact words without identifying them as a quotation.**⁵
- Modifying the words from the source.
- Transcribe words that are irrelevant to your research.
6. Which complex visualization technique is suggested to contribute to successful dissertation research?
- Visualizing stress management.
- Picturing the writing process.
- Envisioning future research impact.**⁶
- I imagine the dissertation defense.
7. What is the primary purpose of the findings chapter in a dissertation?
- To describe data collection methods.
- To interpret data and conclude.
- To discuss the implications of the research.

⁵ Turabian, 370–71.

⁶ James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2nd ed (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 22.

To present raw data for reader analysis.⁷

8. When formulating conclusions based on research findings, which of the following is crucial to ensure consistency?

Restating the research questions in the conclusions.

Ensuring that the findings logically align with each other.⁸

Providing a detailed summary of each interpretation.

Listing all possible interpretations in the consistency chart.

9. Which of the following is NOT a critical factor in ensuring the reasonableness of a recommendation?

Being logically derived from the findings.

Being practical and capable of implementation.

Including a detailed list of all possible suggestions.⁹

I was being both content and context-specific.

10. Which of the following statements is NOT true according to the WHO guidelines for publication acknowledgments?

Financial contributions to the development of the publication should be noted separately from technical contributions.

⁷ Sampson, 61–62.

⁸ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, 4th ed (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2019), 677–79.

⁹ Bloomberg and Volpe, 680–81.

- WHO staff who support the publishing process in the ordinary course of their work should always be acknowledged.¹⁰**
- Acknowledgments should include full names, positions, institutions, cities, and countries for each person acknowledged.
- Financial contributors' names should not be enlarged or highlighted to publicize donors' names.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation : A Road Map from Beginning to End*. 4th ed. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2019.
- Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 5th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024.
- Sampson, P. James. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. 2nd ed. Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017.
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- World Health Organization. *WHO Style Guide*. 2nd ed. World Health Organization, 2013.

¹⁰ World Health Organization, *WHO Style Guide*, 2nd ed (World Health Organization, 2013), 51–51.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.